

Rebutting Drs. DeStefano and Offit's claims of vaccine safety in: Principal Controversies in Vaccine Safety in the United States

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Drs. DeStefano and Offit make many vaccine safety claims in their recent article published in the Clinical Infectious Diseases journal. (1)

DeStefano et al. make their claims based on many epidemiological studies. The US Institute of Medicine committee in their 2011 report (2) on Adverse Effects of Vaccines: Evidence and Causality wrote:

"The committee concluded the evidence convincingly supports 14 specific vaccine–adverse event relationships. In all but one of these relationships, the conclusion was based on strong mechanistic evidence with the epidemiologic evidence rated as either limited confidence or insufficient."

So in an overwhelming 93% (13 of 14) cases, mechanistic evidence provided convincing evidence and epidemiological studies failed to do so. Epidemiological studies are weak, have numerous sources of confounding and offer little value. Epidemiological study results are misinterpreted leading to type II errors. (3) Further, most medical research findings are false, of poor quality and are affected by flagrant conflicts of interest. (4–11) These are important facts to keep in mind while evaluating the claims made by DeStefano et. al.

Fundamental flaws of epidemiological studies

Epidemiological studies make a fundamentally flawed assumption that all MMR vaccines are the same or all Hepatitis B vaccines are the same, for example. Not true. Non-target protein content (as in excipients, residual growth media, residual bacterial/viral/fungal proteins) of vaccines vary between countries, time, vendor, manufacturing facility etc. They are unregulated, there are no specifications (12) or labeling laws.(13) Epidemiological studies ignore such variations and therefore their results from one country do not apply to the next. Result from one year may not apply to the next. Results using vaccines from one vendor or facility is not applicable to another. Arepanrix and Pandemrix vaccine induced narcolepsy is a great example. (14) Both were made by GlaxoSmithKline. Arepanrix made in Canada caused fewer cases of narcolepsy compared to Pandemrix made in Europe (15), due to the difference in H1N1 nucleoprotein content in the vaccines. Egg protein content in influenza vaccines vary by orders of magnitude (16). Milk protein content varied two-fold in just eight vaccine samples. (17)

So studies done in Denmark do not apply to the US, for example.

Autism

DeStefano et al. write: "Numerous studies provide conclusive evidence that MMR vaccine does not cause autism".

Not true. Epidemiological studies they cite, can only show association. They cannot prove causation or lack of causation.

However, the MMR vaccine is likely not the main cause of autism. We provide strong mechanistic evidence that cow's milk protein containing vaccines (DTap/Tdap, Prevnar 13, ActHib, Menactra) cause the vast majority (~75%) of autism cases. (18)

While Menactra may not be commonly administered to young children, it can cause maternal folate receptor alpha antibody (FRAA) mediated autism.

DeStefano et al. write: "Autism is a neurodevelopmental condition that has a strong genetic component and whose genesis begins *in utero*."

DeStefano et al. provide no citation to support the apparent claim that all cases of autism begin *in utero*. Even in case of *in utero* genesis of autism, vaccine induced maternal FRAA (18), maternal anti-GAD65 antibodies (19–22) and other maternal autism related antibodies (23,24) can be the cause. But that applies only to a subset of cases as we have shown. (18)

Thimerosal

Thimerosal is a preservative used in vaccines to protect against bacterial/viral/fungal growth in vaccines. This very fact also means vaccines, single or multi-dose formulations can be contaminated with aeroallergens, the same way they were contaminated with bacterial/viral/fungal organisms. Aeroallergen containing vaccines cause the development of numerous disorders including asthma and seasonal allergies. (25)

Influenza

Discussing influenza vaccines, DeStefano et al. make no mention of influenza vaccines causing the development of allergy to the influenza proteins themselves (IgE mediated sensitization). (26–29) This can result in increased severity of influenza disease due to a concurrent allergic reaction to the influenza viral proteins. This is similar to a secondary dengue infection and therefore, similar to dengue shock syndrome (DSS), we have influenza shock syndrome (ISS). (30,31)

Autoimmunity

DeStefano et al. write: "No mechanisms have been demonstrated to explain how vaccines could account for the development of autoimmune disease"

Not true. We describe a novel mechanism by which vaccines cause the development of autoimmune disorders. (19,21)

DeStefano et al. write: "Autoimmunity involves an immune response directed against self-antigens and mechanisms are present at birth to prevent the development of such responses. The immune system anticipates that self-reactive T cells will be present and has mechanisms to control them."

While there are elements of truth in that statement, it is an oversimplification. The immune system has a major role to play in preventing cancer as well. Cancer is of course cells that are slightly different from self. So the immune system maintains low affinity self reactive (LASR) T cells in the periphery, that recognize antigens that differ by as little as one amino acid residue from self antigens. LASR T cells normally have a role in cancer defense. These LASR T cells when activated can cross-react with self-antigens thus resulting in autoimmunity. Autoimmunity is therefore a sign for good prognosis in some cancers. Vaccines contain numerous animal proteins. These are highly conserved and many have only occasional alteration of amino acid residues compared to human self-antigens. They are ideally suited for recognition by LASR T cells. Activation of LASR T cells occurs due to stimulation of the innate immune system by the vaccine adjuvant or by live viruses in the vaccine. The result is autoimmunity. The details were previously described. (19,21) In other words, injecting numerous animal proteins as vaccine administration does, stimulates a massive anti-cancer immune response. A consequence of which is autoimmunity. This problem is also applicable to biologics because they are derived from Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cells. The CHOPPI bioinformatics tool (32) was created to analyze autoimmunity potential of biologics that contain residual animal proteins. The autoimmunity problem is far worse in vaccines due to immune stimulation with adjuvants and live viruses. Vaccine makers do not perform any such bioinformatics analysis for vaccine safety.

Type 1 diabetes

DeStefano et al. write: " Rigorous epidemiologic studies of infant vaccines and type 1 diabetes found that measles vaccine was not associated with an increased risk for diabetes"

Not true. The statistics do show association between numerous vaccines (including the measles vaccine) and type 1 diabetes. The statistics were misinterpreted, thus resulting in type II errors as I have detailed. (3)

And more importantly, we provide strong mechanistic evidence of animal protein containing vaccines such as the GAD65 protein contaminated chick embryo cell culture derived MMR vaccine causing the development of autoimmune disorders such as type 1 diabetes. (19–21,33)

Multiple sclerosis

DeStefano et al. write: " The possibility that vaccines can cause or exacerbate multiple sclerosis has been evaluated in several epidemiologic studies. Two large case-control studies showed no association between hepatitis B vaccine and multiple sclerosis [21-22]. Hepatitis B, tetanus, or influenza vaccines were found not to exacerbate symptoms of multiple sclerosis "

The acellular pertussis vaccine does not provide mucosal immunity. Therefore vaccine recipients can be subsequently colonized by *B. pertussis*. Such colonization can cause multiple sclerosis. (34)

HPV vaccine

Clinical trials used active comparators thus masking the adverse effects of the HPV vaccine. (35)

Strong mechanistic evidence adds to epidemiological evidence that yeast protein containing HPV vaccines do indeed cause numerous autoimmune disorders. (36)

Aluminum

DeStefano et al. write: "Aluminum salts have safely been used to adjuvant vaccines since the 1930s"

The authors provide no citation to support this claim.

DeStefano et al. write: "Studies have shown that children who receive aluminum-containing vaccines have serum levels of aluminum that are well below the toxic range"

This is irrelevant. The main concern about aluminum is not its direct toxicity. Aluminum salts are used in vaccines because they are an immunological adjuvant. The main concern therefore is immunotoxicity of numerous non-target proteins adsorbed on the surface of these aluminum adjuvant particles, that result in off-target immune responses. (37–39)

DeStefano et al. write: "The authors found no correlation between infant blood or hair aluminum concentrations and vaccine history or between blood aluminum and overall developmental status"

Again irrelevant, as explained, it is not blood or hair concentrations that are important. It is the immunological adjuvant effect occurring in the muscle and lymph nodes. By the time the aluminum is in the blood, the immunological damage has already occurred.

DeStefano et al. write: "A study that evaluated the incidence of autoimmune disease in more than 18,000 patients who received subcutaneous allergen-specific immunotherapy containing large quantities of injected aluminum adjuvants found that patients receiving injected aluminum had a lower incidence of autoimmune disease compared with controls"

Again irrelevant. The aluminum adjuvant had the subcutaneous immunotherapy (SCIT) specific allergen adsorbed on it. In the case of vaccines, animal, fungal, residual bacterial/viral proteins adsorbed on adjuvant particles cause the development of autoimmunity, due to molecular mimicry between these proteins and self-antigens. Therefore, comparison with SCIT does not make sense.

Too many vaccines too soon

Milk containing vaccines cause the development or boost milk allergy. (12,40,41) While one vaccine shot may cause mild allergy, 12 (4xDTaP + 4xPevnar 13 + 4xActHib) milk protein containing

vaccines, repeatedly boost milk IgE mediated sensitization causing life-threatening milk allergy (12,40,42) and autism (18).

DeStefano et al. write: "The immune system of infants is perfectly capable of handling the number of antigens in vaccines"

Agree, but that is not the problem with too many too soon. As shown above, too many non-target protein containing vaccines repeatedly boost off-target immune responses, thus causing numerous disorders.

Conclusion

Vaccine safety claims by DeStefano et al. clearly do not stand up to scrutiny. If vaccines are as safe as claimed, why do vaccine makers need to be protected against liability for their products?

Vaccines cause numerous diseases including life-threatening food allergies (12,40,43), asthma (25,43), autism (18,44) and numerous autoimmune disorders (19,23,36,44–51).

Mechanistic evidence of vaccine safety is needed. Wraith et al. (52) called for autoimmune serology during clinical trials. But that never happens. Verdier (53) and Wraith et al. (52) have called for bioinformatics analysis to avoid molecular mimicry between vaccine components and self-antigens. Never happens.

Current non-target protein containing vaccines are extremely unsafe. All non-target proteins must be immediately removed by processes such as affinity chromatography (54) to improve vaccine safety.

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